

Quantum Bound State Statistics From Classical Free Particle Action?

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In a previous note (1) we argued that both the relativistic $A = -m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and nonrelativistic $A = \frac{1}{2} m v^2$ classical free particle actions may be written with $v = x/t$ and x and t varied independently to yield: $\partial A / \partial x = p$ and $\partial A / \partial t = -E$. Thus A is equivalent to $-Et + px$ for a free particle with x and t being treated as independent. We argue in this note that such an assumption is equivalent to a statistical picture for a free particle even at the classical level because x and t are treated as independent. Thus a constant p may occur at any x because no time is linked to x . Given that all space points are the same for constant p one expects a constant probability at all x points. Knowing p exactly means not knowing anything about which x one has.

Secondly, one may create an ensemble of free particle p classical actions for a situation containing a potential $V(x)$. Given that x and t are independent, there cannot be any notion of single p accelerating, although a v_{rms} from an ensemble may. At a given x (x known exactly) one does not know which p is present. Thus the ideas of uncertainty of p and x follow immediately from this picture.

If one considers a single particle and an ensemble of free particles in the x - t independent scenario, then each free particle action p is linked to $A = -Et + px$ where $E = p^2/2m$. This ensemble would arguably be stirred up by a potential $V(x)$. If one wishes to consider an equilibrium scenario for which there is an overall E_n for the bound system one would expect an overall $E_n t$ for the system and for $-p^2/2m t$ pieces to disappear. Thus we postulate that $p^2/2m + \{p \text{ part}\} G(p's, k's) = E_n$ for all p where $\{p \text{ part}\} G(p's, k's)$ is an unknown function and $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

Next one may consider the spatial situation for which $V(x)$ is the classical potential for a single particle. The kinetic energy follows from an ensemble of free particles with the overall $-Et$ removed. From classical considerations one would expect to have a $KE(x)$. Thus one expects: $KE(x) = \{ \sum_p a(p) f(px) \} / \{ \sum_p a(p) f(px) \}$ with $f(px)$, an orthonormal basis set, because the action contains px . (It is orthonormal because one wishes the identity of p to exist if not at a point, then over all of x .)

We try to argue in this note that $f(px) = \exp(ipx)$, the momentum eigenstate which follows from $A = -Et + px$. We find $G(p's, k's)$ which implies entanglement or mixing of a given p state with other p and k states from the potential $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus one expects an entropy linked to this momentum entanglement. Given the form $\exp(ipx)$, finding a set of a_p 's which satisfy $p^2/2m + G(p's, k's) = E_n$ leads to a spatial distribution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ so there should be an entropy contribution from this spatial part as well. In classical statistical mechanics one has both momentum and spatial contributions to entropy.

We argue for $S = S_p + S_x$, but note that even though px has x, p symmetry as does the Heisenberg uncertainty principle $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$, S_p and S_x may not be symmetric in terms of important parameters such as n , energy level. In other words, S_p the entanglement entropy with $V(x)$ may be the driver entropy sensitive to energy level changes while S_x the resulting spatial density may not be as sensitive. Furthermore the overall entropy $S_p + S_x$ gives

information about uncertainties in x and p as is already known in the literature where bound state $S_p + S_x$ bounds are given.

Free Particle Classical Action

It is known that classical mechanics allows one to follow a particle in time i.e. $x(t)$, $v(t)$, $a(t)$ (acceleration) etc. In other words, a main idea of this classical theory is that x depends on t . In (1), however, we write both the relativistic $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and nonrelativistic $A = t \cdot \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ classical actions in terms of $v=x/t$ and treat x and t as independent. Then:

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial x} = p \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} = -E \quad ((1))$$

Then $A = -Et + px$. This form is already linked to classical wave forms such as sound and light for which velocity = frequency wavelength.

The point we wish to make is that if one has a constant p (i.e. constant v =velocity) and no time in the picture, this p may be equally associated with any x i.e. knowing p exactly means that one knows nothing about x . One, however, expects an equal probability weight at each x .

Consider next a bound state with a classical potential $V(x)$. Instead of using $\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) = E_n$ which assumes that one knows $v(x)$ and hence $x(t)$ from $dx/dt = v(x)$, one may use an ensemble of free particle momenta. Furthermore one expects $KE(x)$ or:

$$KE(x) = \left\{ \sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) f(px) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_p a(p) f(px) \right\} \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{nonrelativistic})$$

We assume $f(px)$ because the classical free particle action contains this term. It is orthonormal because at the least we wish p to have a distinct identity over all space. It is entangled with $V(x)$ at a specific x hence $f(px)$.

Each p , however, should be associated with its own classical action $-\frac{p^2}{2m} t + px$ (for the nonrelativistic case). This assumes that the only effect of the potential is to knock one p into another p' like in two particle classical scattering in a gas which is not the case. We note that given that x and t are independent, a p may occur anywhere. Furthermore we argue that various p states may interact with momentum k states of a potential anywhere as well. If $f(px)$ represents an orthonormal basis, then $V(x) = \sum_k V_k f(kx)$. If one defines a statistical equilibrium as one in which the momentum state time pieces $-\frac{p^2}{2m} t$ disappear with the emergence of an overall new time piece $-t E_n$, then one expects the action of each momentum state to be:

$$-E_n t + px \quad ((3))$$

This suggests that $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ for a momentum state is only part of the picture. In order to achieve ((3)) one may expect:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) + [p \text{ part of}] G(p's, k's) = E_n a(p) \quad ((4))$$

In other words there is entanglement or mixing of momenta k 's from $V(x)$ with many of the $a(p)$'s to create $G(p,s,k,s)$. G is complicated, but may be linked to the spatial scenario.

For the spatial case a single particle has a potential energy of $V(x)$ at x . The kinetic energy is given by ((2)) (nonrelativistic). One may be unsure as to whether $KE(x)+V(x)$ ((5)) equals a constant at each x as in the classical case. Linking ((5)) with ((4)) which contains a constant E_n , however, suggests that:

$$G(p,s,k,s) \text{ for } p_1 = [f(p_1, x) \text{ component of}] \{ \sum \text{over } k V_k f(kx) \sum \text{over } p a(p) f(px) \} \quad ((6))$$

The problem is to find $f(px)$ which should be invariant over space suggesting a periodic type of function. For the classical particle dA/dx partial $=p$ at any x , but further derivatives are 0. Thus a quantum picture requires a further step, namely replacing A with a function of A which allows for one to obtain constant p $f_n(A)$ from d/dx partial $f_n(A)$. This leads to:

$$f_n(A) = \exp(ipx) = f(px) \quad ((7))$$

Thus the quantum wave which follows from an eigenvalue equation linked to $dA/dx = p$ and dA/dt partial $= -E$ gives $\exp(-ipp/2m t + i px)$ as a solution of $f(px-Et)$. One may obtain $G(p,s,k,s)$ and see the entanglement between the p 's and k 's of the potential clearly i.e.

$$a(p) pp/2m + \sum \text{over } k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \quad ((8))$$

In other words, in creating energy for any p there is entanglement of other probabilities $a(p-k)$ with V_k 's from the potential. Given the stochastic nature of the problem which is already established from the classical action with x and t independent, one would expect an entropy describing this $a(p)$ entanglement. A set of $a(p)$'s which satisfy ((8)) (which is equivalent to the time-independent Schrodinger equation) automatically lead to a spatial distribution $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which should also be linked to entropy. Thus there are both momentum and spatial aspects to entropy just as in the case of classical statistical mechanics.

To calculate entropy directly one may consider Shannon's entropy $-\sum \text{over } i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. Here $P(i)$ are real, positive and less than one and sum to 1. $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ is complex, but it may be shown (2) that it is linked to classical probabilities $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ through $a(p)a(p)$ and $W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state. Thus we argue that a fictitious state $P(p)P(x)$ (because p and x cannot be known exactly at the same time) describes the probability of the quantum bound state even though it is really created through the entanglement of $a(p)$'s with V_k from $V(x)$ together with the resulting spatial $W(x)$. Thus:

$$S = S_p + S_x \text{ where } S_p = - \sum \text{over } p a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)a(p)) - \sum \text{over } x W(x)W(x) \ln(W(x)W(x)) \quad ((9))$$

It may be noted that $a(p)$'s and $W(x)$ yield momentum and spatial weights and so should be linked to the notion that one does not know x and p exactly. Thus there is an alternative measure to Heisenberg's $\text{Var}(x)\text{Var}(p)$, namey S_p+S_x which has a lower bound listed regularly in the literature.

Lack of Symmetry in S_p and S_x

The classical action contains px as does the resulting quantum $\exp(ipx)$. In addition Heisenberg's $\text{Var}(p)\text{Var}(x)$ is symmetrical in p and x . Even $S=S_p+S_x$ appears to be symmetrical, but the two variables play different roles. We argued above that S_p is due to entanglement of $a(p)$'s with V_k 's from $V(x)$ and that given set of $a(p)$'s, $W(x)$ follows and is linked to spatial uncertainty (i.e. $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$). If one calculates S_p and S_x for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls one finds that although there is a relationship between L the box size in S_p and S_x , there is no such relationship for n , the energy level. In particular S_x does not depend on n , but S_p does. Thus one needs to be careful when considering $P(x)P(p)$ which treats p and x in a symmetrical way. The underlying $a(p)$, $W(x)$ physics seems to define the quantum bound state problem and the fictitious state probability $P(x)P(p)$ is simply a convenient way to calculate the entropy of a more a difficult problem i.e. the momentum entanglement and its associated $W(x)$ spatial weight.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that treating x and t as independent in the free particle relativistic or nonrelativistic classical action A leads to $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$. This introduces linear operators d/dx and d/dt associated with p and x , but also immediately establishes the statistical nature of the scenario. In particular, if x and t are independent one may not write $x(t)$ which is a main strategy of classical mechanics. Instead a constant p may be associated with any x . This is already a quantum mechanical idea as is the use of $d/dx \text{ partial}$ for p and $d/dt \text{ partial}$ for $-E$. This is, however, not the full quantum picture yet. If one considers an ensemble of free particle actions as a solution of a single particle in a classical potential, one needs to introduce $f(px)$ i.e. orthonormal basis functions associated with p in order that average kinetic energy be a function of x . Given that x and t are independent and one cannot know $x(t)$, $V(x)$ cannot cause the acceleration of any given free particle p , but it can cause the acceleration of vrms. The classical action contains $-Et+px$ where $E=pp/2m$ for a free particle, but if one assumes a statistical equilibrium one may postulate that individual E 's disappear from the problem giving way to a single Ent i.e. each p is associated with $-\text{Ent}+px$. In such a case, one expects:

$pp/2m a(p) + G(p's, k's) (p \text{ part}) = E_n a(p)$. This should be a coefficient of $f(px)$. If that is the case then: $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)f(px)$ and $G(p's,k's) = (p \text{ part of }) V(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k a(p-k)$ if $V(x)= \text{Sum over } k V_k f(kx)$ where $f(kx)$ is an orthonormal basis.

One finally needs to find $f(px)$ which should be linked to the classical action scenario. The classical action is $-Et+px$, but if one wishes to have an invariant function which allows for information about all powers of E and p and is linked to $d/dt \text{ partial}$ and $d/dx \text{ partial}$ then $f(px)=\exp(ipx-iEt)$ is the solution. We suggest this should be $f(px)$ and see that: $pp/2m a(p) + \text{Sum over } k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p)$ shows entanglement of $a(p)$'s with V_k 's of the potential.

Given that one has a stochastic system with this entanglement, one would expect a momentum entropy. The $a(p)$'s, however, lead to $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which suggests spatial weighting so there should be spatial entropy as well. How may one calculate overall

entropy? We note that $a(p)$ and $W(x)$ may be converted into classical probabilities $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$ (see (2)) and suggest using Shannon's entropy for the fictitious state $P(x)P(p)$. (It is as if one knows p and x at the same time.)

One finds that $S=S_p+S_x$. We argue this should be a measure of uncertainty in x and p as $a(p)$'s and $W(x)$'s are used and it is well known that in the literature a lower bound for S_p+S_x is given for a bound state. Furthermore we argue that even though x and p appear on equal footing in $P(p)P(x)$ or $\exp(ipx)$ or S_p+S_x , the physics occurs at the $a(p)$, $W(x)$ level (time-independent Schrodinger equation level). If one calculates S_p and S_x for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls one finds that $S_p(n)$ and S_x does not, where n is the energy level. Thus the physical nature of the two entropies is very different. $S_p(n)$ seems to be very important as it shows the actual entanglement occurring with $V(x)$. Once a set of $a(p)$'s are found, $W(x)$ follows.

References

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